

Why could coordination failure result in poverty traps? Suppose that you are a policy-maker in a low-income country. What policy would you implement to overcome coordination failure? What are the implications and challenges of implementing the policy?

(ES30035: Coursework)

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Section A, question 4 (2419 words)

Coordination failure occurs when there exist two equilibria. Agents start off in the less optimal equilibrium, where if coordinated, can collectively move to an improved equilibrium that is pareto preferred on a societal level. However, as agents are not aware of the complementarities present, they are trapped in the initial equilibrium. [Kraay and McKenzie \(2014\)](#) define poverty trap as a set of “self-reinforcing mechanisms whereby countries start poor and remain poor”. Using the Solow model, we can show how poverty trap can be a result of coordination failure.

The model states in each period, agents save a fraction s of their output per capita:

$$y = Ak^a$$

Where A is productivity provided by the level of technology. Hence, we denote their investment into capital as sy . The evolution of capital per capita k is:

$$k^* = sy - (\delta + n)k = sAk^a - (\delta + n)k \quad (1)$$

$(\delta + n)k$ denotes the depreciation of capital. δ is the depreciation rate and n is the population growth rate, where the higher the country's population, the lower k will be. k^* denotes the universal steady state level of capital per capita.

The condition above implies that, if $sAk^a > (\delta + n)k$, the amount of capital invested is greater than the amount of capital that depreciates. Given diminishing marginal return of investment and linear depreciation, k will increase until the amount gained from investment is outweighed by depreciation. After which, k will decrease, until investment and depreciation offset one another and vice versa:

$$sAk^a = (\delta + n)k$$

Figure 1: Solow model with poverty trap

In the context of a low-income country with poor institutional quality, we will assume that its domestic market is relatively small, having under-developed sectors, which operate at a low aggregate level of industrialization. Firms use traditional technology A^* , produces homogenous goods and generates a normal profit under perfect competition. Hence, investment is sA^*k^a and the economy operates in steady state k^1 .

In figure 1, k^1 is located to the left of z , denoting a threshold level of k , where if this economy manages to accumulate to, can move to an improved investment curve and enjoy a higher steady state level of capital per capita $k^2 > k^1$ through having higher productivity. Given z 's position to k^1 , it would be impossible for this economy to grow their way out of k^1 .

Suppose this model country receives an aid which increased their capital stock to k^3 , resulting in:

$$sA^*k^a > (\delta + n)k$$

Due to set country still operates using A^* , and is on investment curve sA^*k^a ; according to eqn(1), the economy will see a reduction in k until $k^* = k^1$. Hence, we see no improvement in output $y = A^*k^a$, and the economy remains trapped in poverty at k^1 . Therefore, the only way for this economy to grow beyond k^1 is to move to the higher investment curve $sA^{**}k^a$, by innovating its technology and improving their productivity, through coordination.

Developing upon previous assumptions, given homogenous goods, consumers in this economy will evenly distribute their consumption across N goods, produced by different sectors. With each sector producing x_i number of goods, at price p_i , expenditure for sector i is:

$$x_i p_i = \frac{Y}{N} \quad (2)$$

As price is exogenously given, we normalise it to 1 for simplicity. Hence $x_i = \frac{Y}{N}$.

In each sector, there are two types of firms – ones that utilises traditional technology and ones which has sufficient knowledge to transition to modern technology and become a monopolist. Through traditional technology, one unit of labour L_t produces one unit of goods¹. With perfect competition where $\pi_t = 0$, wage w_t is equal to price multiplied by marginal product of labour:

$$1 \times p_i = w_t = 1$$

As of productive modern technology, one unit of labour L_m is turned into $a > 1$ unit of output. Given goods remain homogenous, monopolists are price limited and cannot charge more than traditional firms:

$$p_m = p_i = 1$$

1: This would result in a 45-degree production line.

Figure 2: Production in a Big Push Model

Using modern technology A_{new} means facing two additional costs. Firstly, there are fixed cost associated – for example, nuclear power plants need to be licensed and built before operation. This implies that modern firms will need F labours to start producing, as illustrated by figure 2. Beyond F , each worker can produce more efficiently, as shown by its steeper slope of α . Hence, with labour evenly distributed across all sectors, at $\frac{L}{N}$, modern firms have a positive output gap versus traditional firms, denoted by point A to B.

Secondly, workers need to learn to operate modern machineries, and experiences disutility of $v > 1$ for their effort. To compensate, modern firms have to offer a wage premium:

$$w_m = 1 + v > w_t = 1$$

We can now compute the monopolist's profit function, which given complementarities, is increasing to the number of industrialising firms n :

$$\pi_m(n) = \left(1 - \frac{w_m}{a}\right) \frac{Y(n)}{N} - w_m F \quad (3)$$

With $p_m = 1$, $1 - \frac{w_m}{a}$ is the profit from 1 unit of good as $\frac{w_m}{a}$ is the cost of producing one unit of good using A_{new} ; multiplied by $\frac{Y(n)}{N}$ which is the quantity demanded, minus the fixed cost $w_m F$. There are two complementarities at work here:

Figure 3: Complementarity reducing average cost of adopting modern technology

The first complementarity is that average cost of adopting is decreasing to n . In figure 3, both cost curves are negative and diminishing to n because of this. Intuitively, as the market size for modern technology A_{new} grows, we experience increasing returns to scale which causes the cost of adoption to lower. Fixed cost wise, it becomes easier to install machines as its supply chains grows. Variable cost wise, machines become cheaper to maintain and instead of needing to train workers from the ground up, there will be workers available in the market with relevant skills.

By remaining traditional, the N firms in this sector experience an average cost of AC_{old} at point A. Hence, for them to move to A_{new} , the new average cost must equate to AC_{old} . The minimum threshold for this is for $x + 1$ number of firms to adopt collectively, denoted by point E. Hence, if $n > x + 1$ number of firms adopt A_{new} collectively, each of them experiences a cost reduction from point A to D. Rest of the traditional firms know that by adopting A_{new} , they will improve their profit, through a decrease in average cost. Given firms are profit maximising, they will industrialise and enjoy the lowest average cost possible for this sector at point B. This is the pareto preferred equilibrium k_2 in figure 1.

On the contrary, if complementarity is ignored, and there is a coordination failure resulting in only $n < x + 1$ adopting A_{new} , these n firms will experience an increase in average cost from Point A to F. By sticking with A_{old} , they would be better off. Hence, they would move back to using A_{old} . This is the trap equilibrium caused by coordination failure k_1 .

Figure 4: Complementarity of demand spillover from wage premium

The second complementarity is the demand spillovers for good x_i . The total GDP of this economy is made up of profit earned by firms, and wage earned by their respective workers (w_m, w_t):

$$Y = \pi_m + \pi_t + w_m L_m + w_t L_t \quad (4)$$

For potential monopolists, despite having the knowledge to industrialise, they would only do so if their pay-off is higher. Knowing $\pi_t = 0$, they would only adopt if $\pi_m(n) \geq 0$. Hence, eqn(4) becomes:

$$Y = \pi_m + w_m L_m + w_t L_t \quad (5)$$

We can infer from eqn(5) that as more firms adopt A_{new} , the demand for L_m will increase. With $w_m > w_t$, and $\pi_m(n) \geq 0$, this economy becomes richer ($Y \uparrow$). In a low-income country with imperfect credit markets, and given that there is high risk aversion, they are unlikely to invest in profitable but risky projects (Morduch, 1990). Hence, households derive utility solely from consumption of goods:

$$u = \sum_{i=1}^n \ln(x_i)$$

Therefore, when consumers' income increases due to the wage premium v , they would increase the quantity of goods demanded evenly across all sectors, indiscriminately for both modern and traditional firms. Using eqn(2), given the number of sectors and price of goods remains unchanged, x_i increase from x_{it} upwards to x_{im} as show in figure 4:

$$x_{im} = \frac{Y(\uparrow)}{N(\rightarrow)}$$

When $x + 1$ number of firms adopts A_{new} , benefit of demand spillover for monopolists' revenue will equate the cost of v , at which they are indifferent between A_{new} and A_{old} , as shown in figure 4. Hence, if number of adopting firms $n > x + 1$, due to increased demand, they would earn a profit of point D to E:

$$\pi_m(n) > \pi_t = 0$$

Hence, given profit maximising behaviour, firms would all switch to modern technology, and the economy arrives at the pareto preferred equilibrium k^2 (Point B). If $n < x + 1$, those n firms will experience a loss of point G to H:

$$\pi_m(n) < \pi_t = 0$$

Since they are better off at point A, these n firms will move back to using A_{old} . Hence, the economy is back at the trap equilibrium k^1 .

Therefore, in an economy with two stable equilibria, the key for policymakers is to ensure number of firms coordinating for industrialisation n surpasses the threshold $x + 1$, beyond which market will collectively industrialise. Given coordination failure, the only way for them to eliminate the trap equilibrium is by making the pareto preferred equilibrium as easy to achieve as possible, where $x + 1 \rightarrow 1$. Hence, the below condition has to satisfy:

$$\pi_m(1) = \frac{[a - (1 + v)]L - NaF - a(N - 1)Fv}{(N - 1)a + 1} > 0$$

The denominator must be positive given firms will closedown if profit is negative, observe only the nominator:

$$[a - (1 + v)]L - NaF - a(N - 1)Fv > 0$$

$$a > \frac{(1 + v)L}{L - NF - (N - 1)Fv} \quad (6)$$

With exogenous N, L , eqn(6) shows that there are three components to ensuring $\pi_m(1) > 0$: decrease the fixed cost ($F \downarrow$)² associated with industrialisation, decrease the variable cost ($v \downarrow$), and increase the pay-off of modernising by making A_{new} even more productive ($a \uparrow$).

2: By decreasing F , denominator of eqn(6) becomes smaller, decreasing right-hand side, making the condition easier to achieve.

exceed for the big push, especially when administrative capacity is limited for low-income countries. Hence, government policy is likely to be suboptimal.

Figure 6: A reduction in wage premium

Variable cost of A_{new} in this model stems from the wage premium. If v is sufficiently small so that w_m curve is below the revenue curve for A_{new} , it would be easier for firms to generate a positive profit from industrialising, as shown by the positive distance from point D to C in figure 6, which with a higher w_m curve, would have been negative. Given the positive demand spillover from higher wage, policymakers should maintain the absolute level of wage w_m but lower the wage premium paid by firms v . Hence, the government can contribute in the form of a per-worker subsidy s :

$$w_m = (v - s) + s + w_t$$

With s , the wage premium firms face is lowered to $v - s$, in effect causing the w_m curve to shift down to $w_m - s$, as shown in figure 6. With this policy, modern workers are still paid w_m , and complementarities with demand is still present, whilst the threshold for industrialisation is lower. This in turn making it less risky for firms to innovate as less firms need to collectively coordinate $n(\downarrow)$ for this economy to move to the pareto preferred equilibrium.

In practice, wage premium is not the only variable cost firms face when industrialising. For example, there might be a higher maintenance fee for the machinery, given only few engineers have the relevant skill. Variable costs will decrease as the market size of A_{new} increase, but it is expensive to grow the market. Hence, policy described suffers similar issues cost wise as the fixed cost policy.

Even in a setting where all other variable costs are homogenous across traditional and modern sector, the per-worker subsidy can be abused due to asymmetric information. Given institutions are less developed in a low-income country, firms can falsely report their employee count to lower its cost knowing that the chance of being punished is low. Hence, it is easy for budget to be allocated incorrectly.

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